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CYBERCRIME AND TECHNOLOGICAL GADGETS

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Abstract: *The article shows how gadgets and newly manufactured devices affect the world in the era of modernized information technologies, as well as how they create opportunities to make people's lives easier. At a time when information technology is rapidly developing it is shown that the concepts of information security, cyber security and cyber crime are increasing in importance. The importance of cybercrimes, their types and methods of committing, issues of prevention of cybercrimes are highlighted. Active users of digital technologies are in the digital world, digital it is said that it is a vital necessity to follow the culture and take measures to protect oneself from cybercrimes.*

Keywords: *Articleshows, gadgets, negative, lifestyle, education, technological system, social networking, human services, digital technologies, information security, cyber security, cybercrime, digital culture.*

КИБЕРПРЕСТУПНОСТЬ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГАДЖЕТЫ

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Аннотация: *В статье показано, как гаджеты и новые устройства влияют на мир в эпоху модернизированных информационных технологий, а также как они создают возможности облегчить жизнь людей. В то время, когда информационные технологии стремительно развиваются, показано, что понятия информационной безопасности, кибербезопасности и киберпреступности приобретают все большее значение. Освещены значение*

киберпреступлений, их виды и способы совершения, вопросы предотвращения киберпреступлений. Активные пользователи цифровых технологий находятся в цифровом мире, говорят, что следить за культурой и принимать меры по защите от киберпреступлений — это жизненная необходимость.

Ключевые слова: Статьи-шоу, гаджеты, негатив, образ жизни, образование, технологическая система, социальные сети, социальные услуги, цифровые технологии, информационная безопасность, кибербезопасность, киберпреступность, цифровая культура.

Introduction. In this fast moving world, gadgets and electronic devices play an essential role with the help of science and technology. therefore, without a doubt, every person meet a range of modern gadgets in daily life. Consequently, in our modern world, humanity hinge on them almost. using recent gadgets and emerging technologies, especially, scientists invent artificial intelligence that gives an opportunity to do arduous works which harmful for human health. according to scientists says, artificial intelligence and modern gadgets are invented as servants for human rights. An example of this is that many artificial intelligences are being developed to care for the olds. Mainly, in Japan the old people always suffer from dementia and japanese scientists have developed high-tech technology for the elderly and patients whodo not have any relations or friends and now they are serving as good nursing care.

The usage of innovative pedagogical technologies in education is the demand of the times and serves to imorove the quality of education. In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure in the lesson. Therefore, modern teaching methods - interactive methods, innovative technologies play an important role in the training of qualified professionals in higher educational institution and faculties. For the most part, interactive methods of pedagogic technoogy ensure that students have an educated, mature qualification. Using of technology not only has higher influece in students but also in teachers too. Kaite J. Carstens said that flipped classroom method is being used by most teachers now and students can study at home and engage proactively in discussions, activities and exercises occuring in school. Impediments in education such a fulltime job and illness is technically no more an obstacle due to virtual classrooms happening via modern technologies. Technology has supplied the students the flexibility to maximize their studying time.

Methods. In the 21st century, digital technologies have become an integral part of our lives. The use of information technology brings various conveniences to our daily life entered, dramatically increased our work efficiency. We are from information technology. In addition to regular use, there is another important concept, this is the concept of information security. Users of information technologies threats to information security are increasing as the number increases. The same at the time, information has become a power that knows no bounds, and it affects the entire population of the world it is no exaggeration to say that he is in charge. It has become the largest global space the internet is a weapon that affects not only the individual, but also the security of society and the state is also turning. In our country, every citizen has the information he wants the right to receive and use is guaranteed by law. But of these possibilities There are also people who use it for their own dirty purposes. They are poisoning people's minds in the virtual world, eyeing other people's wealth and so on by performing actions related to gaining the dignity of a person, resorting to crime. It is through this that the process of globalization enters our lives introduced the concept of "cybercrime". Cybercrime is being committed in virtual space It is considered a crime, and it ranks 4th among the crimes committed in the world. But new types of crimes appear every year in the global network. Such threats can be called general cybercrime. Cybercrime is a technological type of crime the difference from ordinary crimes is that science and technology, computer and is the use of information technologies, radioelectronics achievements.

Cybercrime differs from ordinary crime primarily in the fact that it is committed does: when real criminals use guns to commit crimes, cybercriminals computer to commit social crimes use technologies. Most of the cybercrimes we see represents the migration of true crime into cyberspace. Cybercriminals computer fraud, theft, stalking, extortion and other crimes used to achieve Their use of computer technology does not fundamentally change the legal definition of the activity in question; fraud, no matter how it is done it is still fraud. But cybercriminals use computer technology extensively important because it allows them to commit crimes on a large scale gives and much more to law enforcement agencies to identify and catch them makes it difficult. Responsible employees of the Cyber Security Center of the Ministry of Internal Affairs at AOKA in the last 3 years, it was reported at the press conference with the participation of the number of cybercrimes in our country has increased several times.

It is noted that there are more than 25 million Internet users in Uzbekistan. The results of the analysis show that the trend of cybercrime growth is being observed in our country today. Today, the most popular cybercrimes are as follows:

- fraudsters take the codes from the SMS messages sent to the plastic card users under the pretext of making a payment or giving the winnings and embezzling the funds from it;

- threatening to acquire and disclose personal information extortion (cyber extortion);

- cases of intimidation, insults, suicide with the use of force in the social network (cyberbullying) and others.

The most effective way to fight against threats on the Internet is early warning of possible dangers by forming a culture of Internet use in the population. The "Cyber-assistant" platform was also developed by the Cyber Security Center of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In addition, the Law "On Cyber Security" adopted in 2022 has greatly regulated relations in the field of cyber security.

Nevertheless, every person enters the digital world and is active in digital technologies while using it, adhere to digital culture and personal digital hygiene needs to do.

How can technologies make life easier and safer?

As we know, technological equipments and gadget are used almost every time and in our modern era, humanity need to use digitals for living easier and safer. How true is this statement ? There are some great ways to prove that life is uncomplicated with technology.

1. Better healthcare through technology

In fact, technology is really depend on health, technically, healthcare has been changed so much because of technology. It would be difficult to say all the exciting developments of the past year. Even if we pay attention simply on the latest equipments, such as clinic tools which managing the platform, it can be seen how important technology has become in human services as a whole.

2. More secure online transactions through technology

In spite of cybercrime is on the top, there is a number of ways for internet users to protect themselves. The Apple Pay, for example, can create an opportunity for users to save their sensitive and personal informations as well as credit card details in a single location. Regardless of which choises you shoose , such kind of technology can help keep your informations safely.

3. Easier shopping and grocery purchasing

When you are too busy with your works, you can shop online in any time and anywhere. Interestingly, you do not have to wait an order or you do not need to go anywhere for purchasing. This is especially true, if you buy something, delivery servise is ready.

4. Smart cities

As all of us know, occasion of environment is not as good as the past time years. Hovewer, against to this problem, scientists invented new technology system that's task is recycling rubbish and provide the whole city with fresh water by reprocessing. Smart cities do not only the envirnment better, but also they use information and communication technology to improve functional efficiency, exchange information with the public, and ensure a higher level of government service and public welfare.

5. Technology: bringing families together

There are several essential social networking sites such as Email, Facebook, Skype, messaging make easier all over the world to stay in touch. According to the researches, public who use Facebook on a regular basis have a 30% boost in the intimacy of their friends, relations, parents. In addition to this, you can find new friends all over the world what you want from any nation or religion as well as it gives an opportunity to meet new nationality, taditions and knowladge.

6. GPS technology

We have herd about horror accidents making poor driving or not to know new roads. Instead of using map for finding a way, GPS gives us step-bby-step voice diretions to navigate. this makes easier for every driver to keep their eyes on the road.

Summary. What happened if there is no any technology and gadgets in our modern life? So, I can freely say that, since invented the telephones, people,s lives changed to simple shape. an example of this idea, if someone need to contact with another one, that person has to go there or write a letter. technology is the aplication of conceptual knowladge for reaching pracical goals, especially in a reproducible way. The concept of technology also means the prducts resulting from efforts.

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